

Challenges for Mobile Marketing in India

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Abstract

In India, mobile communications have been the most visible manifestation of the extraordinary digital accomplishments seen in the past decade. In modern information and communication age, the mobile application is one of the most concerned and rapidly developing areas. Mobile marketing has been considered a new form of marketing and provided new opportunities for companies to do businesses. Marketing activities conducted via mobile devices enable advertisers to directly communicate with potential customers at a fast speed and regardless of the geographical location. Mobile advertising has been recently referred as one of the best means to cut through the clutter and interact directly with the consumer. Hence, with the trend toward direct, one-to-one marketing, more attention is being paid to the use of the mobile channel as a means of effectively advertising to consumers. Indian mobile market is one of the fastest growing markets due to the increase in the number of middle-income consumers and is forecasted to reach millions of users in the next decade. Thus, research on mobile marketing would impact greatly on the way business is done. The current study is an attempt to study consumer responsiveness to mobile marketing, regarding its impact on purchase decision making. The primary objective is to understand the perception of mobile users towards mobile marketing/advertising and their utility value regarding the impact on the purchase decision. The study also aims to concretize some features enhancing the acceptability/ utility of mobile marketing/advertising and suggests an appropriate strategic initiative for the same.

Introduction

There's no doubt we're living in an amplified world. What does that mean? Apps are not just on our phones- they're on our watches, in our cars and the best websites are apps. Apps are the primary way people expect to access information and interact with brands. As apps become a way of life, brands must evolve and mature their mobile marketing strategies and apply new tactics and techniques. App marketing has indeed evolved in recent years. In 2013, marketers focused on user acquisition. In 2014 and 2015 people spending almost 90% of their time on media through apps, the focus was on engagement - and how to use data to improve user interaction. These efforts have paid off; people spent 21 percent more time in apps and app retention is at an all-time high.

The Emergence of Mobile Marketing

After the launch of 3G and 4G digital network, the mobile users started gathering information through their mobiles on the internet. Soon the access to social media made mobiles a very handy tool. Due to the progression of the usage of mobile; mobile marketing came into the picture. Mobile marketing made reaching customers look like a comparatively easy task. The different operating system like Android, Symbian, and IOS supported applications. Mobile marketing used an application to their advantage. Mobiles soon started being seen as one of the popular channels for marketing; it was an opportunity which the marketers were ready to encash. Due to the mobile portal, many marketers were now able to reach end consumers with much lower costs as compared to the traditional marketing promotion and could build a relationship with the customer. This relationship was more interactive as marketers could now customize the message, or in other words 'customerization'. They identified customer not only in the position of personal identity but also regarding geographical location, commercial behavior and social and communication patterns.

Mobile Penetration

On June 16th, 2014, Morgan Stanley reported the average growth rate of Smartphone in India is 25% due to the falling prices, and that the penetration is increasing. It has estimated that by 2018 fiscal, the number will be 519 million. The report also stated that the internet users would rise to 330 million by 2016 financial year driven by higher Smartphone penetration, falling handset costs, faster bandwidth and higher internet content or online services. According to the report the Smart phones in India has witnessed a huge price drop; they have down from \$200 to \$50 in the last two years. As per the Avendus Report, there are over 36 million Smart phones in India¹¹. The report said that over 40% of the Google searches and 9% of the overall webpage view in India comes from mobile devices. Also, it said that 30% of India's Facebook users are mobile users only.

Consumer Acceptance and Response to Mobile Marketing

In 21st-century customer is the king, every company stands by that. Customers are to be reached by various channels but in today's world, mobile marketing communication is the one which reaches more end customers. Marketing of the product is done for creating a positive impression of the brand, for better brand recall, to increase sales and to generate awareness. In today's world customer carry their mobiles everywhere to access anything anytime. Nonetheless, a basic understanding of mobile media and mobile marketing campaign is necessary to develop a successful mobile marketing campaign. Customer in this fast moving life does not have time for something they don't need. A company has to customize and then target their customer. With the help of customer relationship management, any company can know about what our customer's preferences and taste. A company needs to target them very carefully else it generates a negative impression. Customers generally prefer any promotion which takes prior permission; this way customer can be customized. The mobile advertising is much more interactive and personal than traditional advertising. In spite of this, the personal and interactive nature of the phenomenon is not present in the conceptualisations or descriptions of mobile advertising.

Challenges for Mobile Marketing in India

Mobile marketing being in a very nascent but growing stage in India faces some serious challenges. There are some impediments that hinder the mass access to content on mobile phones in India. These comprise the dearth of knowledge about the media with marketers, browser setbacks that lead to poor content quality and heavy data charges for accessing internet on mobile. It is important to address the below-listed issues before adopting this medium for marketing strategies.

1. Knowledge about the media: Although mobile marketing has gained a lot of attention, its true potential is still unknown to many people. There is still very little knowledge available to the consumers as well as marketers concerning mobile as media. Awareness does not necessarily pertain to using the medium, but also how to tackle it and handle it. It is evident that today's marketers in India have still not been able to appreciate the power and attention mobile deserves as a medium.
2. Regulations for marketers: Consumer's rights protection is one of the crucial ways in which today's business houses can retain the trust and loyalty of subscribers, hence it calls for regulations as well. Spam messages have invaded mobile phones as well today after hijacking the internet. Today what we lack is a set of guidelines and regulations specifically for marketers. This can pose the serious threat to customer retention and will end up jamming the inboxes of users with irrelevant content. MMA has braced up to tackle this task before it assumes an indestructible form.
3. Consistency issues of execution: The mobile has simplified the identification of target audience for certain products or services. Still, businesses face hassles to launch any marketing campaign over mobile networks. Several companies still fail to locate and identify their customers. They are dicey even about which tool to be utilized for marketing- MMS or SMS. It is difficult to design a standard campaign since the diversity in handsets is huge in India. Identifying the user and other details such as user session, browser or device would be a herculean task for marketers and is a matter of grave concern. Similarly, the timing of the marketing message delivery is an issue the industry and marketers at large are grappling with today. Information about customer preferences, handsets, geographies, etc., should be analyzed before mobile media strategies are formulated, or campaigns are deployed.
4. Measurement and conversion rates: The response rates produced by the mobile media have been very promising. But the conversion rate has been quite low. Using the medium through customized targeting is the need of the hour (www.canvasm.com, 2010).
5. Marketing data issues: Companies from various sectors are still clueless as to what and how to do it with mobile as a marketing medium. Moreover, lack of marketing data on consumer usage pattern and preferences, etc. add to reluctance on jumping on the medium for campaigns (www.canvasm.com, 2010).
6. Exorbitant Internet data charges: Consumers from almost all the socio-economic strata have started accessing the internet on their mobile phones. Still, the access charges are very high. This can be a probable reason for the delay in implementing mobile marketing strategies (www.canvasm.com, 2010).

Conclusion

Mobile marketing is a very important tool for marketing and is playing the very important role in today's scenario. It not only helps the customer to shop through a verity of product within a few seconds, from anywhere and anytime but also helps the retailers to target their desired customer with extreme ease. Mobile marketing is the latest trend in the market and is extremely powerful too. Through mobile marketing, retailers can reach a bulk of the desired customer anytime without making much effort. However mobile marketing is not that much famous among Indians, but still, they are adopting this latest concept and are looking forward to its exploration. It is a big deal to sell products online in the Indian market where the customer is in the habit of touching and analyzing the product before making the purchase decision. And introducing mobile for online shopping is entirely a different thing. To promote it among students needs continuous efforts and advancement in technology that can make the shopping experience more easy and interesting for the customer.

Today customers are looking forward to the technology that can not only save their time but also can prove trust worthy. According to the mobile apps of the online retailers should be easy going and should insure the security of their personal information too. The de-motivating factor for mobile marketing was the security of their personal information. This shows that however students are adopting mobile marketing for shopping but still they have less trust in the online retailers regarding the security of their personal information. To generate great revenues retailers should focus on winning the trust of their customers by building strongly safe and secure mobile services so that youths can rely on them and can make the purchase without any fear. But the mentality of Indian customer is that they want more in less with good quality too.

So the retailers should come with products that can better fit with their pockets and can grab their attention. As already discussed the Indian economy is increasing enormously and with the increasing economy demand of Indian consumers is increasing too. Indians are adopting mobile marketing gradually and their expectation level is increasing too. In coming years mobile marketing will become the trend of shopping online. Now it becomes the need of the hour to raise the standard of mobile services and to meet the expectation level of the consumers and to earn customer loyalty. It is the high time for the fashion retailers to invent new and innovative ways to grab the attention of youths and to generate desired revenues.

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